

Maintenance of National Values, the Role of Indonesian Language as Nationalism

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the position and function of Indonesia can be the basis for fostering a spirit of nationalism among young people and students. In this case, Indonesian has two positions, namely as a national language and a state language. In its position as a national language, the language functions as a symbol of national pride, national identity, a means of communication between citizens, between regions and between cultures, and a means of unifying ethnicity, culture and language in the archipelago. Meanwhile, in its position as a state language, Indonesian functions as an official state language, a language of education, a means of communication at the national level and a tool for developing culture, science and technology. Remembering the importance of the position and function of the Indonesian language, the author invites young people and students to maintain and continue to develop so that the Indonesian language continues to survive and develop in the future

INTRODUCTION

Indonesian is a language with a long history, both spoken and written. Malay language has existed in the archipelago since the time of the kingdoms. Arifin (2008:5) states that evidence that Malay was used throughout the archipelago is found in various ancient slates, such as the kedukan and talang tuo inscriptions in Palembang, the limestone city inscriptions in West Banka, and many more.

Malay language, which is the basis of Indonesian, already had a role and status in its time. which is very important, both in terms of government and also in everyday life. Many people from other countries come to the archipelago with various types of languages, so Malay is used as a relevant language. which is the source of the Malay language does not recognize the levels of other languages, so it helps its users, so it can be decided that the Malay language which forms the basis of Indonesian already has these functions and a certain place in society. Since the colonial era until the era of globalization, Indonesian has developed very quickly both in spoken and written form. starting with the Van Ophuijsen, Soewandi, and Melindo spellings to the refined spelling that we currently use. The increasing number of activities related to the Indonesian language, such as language research and seminars, as well as language congresses held every year, shows how important the language is in the government and society of the Republic of Indonesia.

Based on the explanation above, every Indonesian citizen should feel proud and protect Indonesian as our unified and national language. However, in fact, many Indonesian students and teenagers are more proud of foreign languages than their own. This shows that young people and students more often use foreign languages when interacting and learning than using Indonesian. Apart from that, combining slank with Indonesian destroys the rules and spellings of the Indonesian language, making students accustomed to using them incorrectly.

Because they do not know or understand the position and role of Indonesian in the Republic of Indonesia, young people and students do not have a deep love for Indonesian. There is no sense of nationalism towards Indonesian because environmental factors, such as where you live, where you socialize and where you get your education, do not support the use of Indonesian properly. Indonesian is still considered official and uninteresting by students and teenagers. Indonesian is increasingly marginalized in the eyes of the young and educated because the home environment, socialization and school are dominated by prokem language and are rarely used well and correctly. If the above problems are not addressed immediately, they will give rise to more complicated problems and be more difficult to resolve. As a result, hopes for the progress of the Indonesian language in the future will only remain hopes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Based on the description above, the author will provide a little information about the paper which aims to increase understanding of the position and function of the Indonesian language in the eyes of young people, students and general readers. The title of the paper written by the author is "Maintaining National Values and the Role of the Indonesian Language as the Main Pillar of Nationalism." The hope is that this paper will be able to encourage, grow and encourage young people and students.

The purpose of writing this paper is to provide an understanding of the role and position of the Indonesian language as the basis for the spirit of nationalism among young people and students, according to the problem formulation.

It is hoped that this paper will help: The author, teach scientific writing skills as well as a tool to measure the author's understanding of the position and function of the Indonesian language. To foster a sense of nationalism towards the Indonesian language, pupils and students must learn about its role and function. General readers can see how important Indonesian is for the Republic of Indonesia and that we as good Indonesian citizens must be able to maintain and maintain Indonesian as the language of the unity and integrity of the Republic of Indonesia.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is literature study, namely a method of collecting data by understanding and studying theories from various literature related to research (Adlini, MN, Dinda, AH, Yulinda, S., Chotimah, O., Merliyana, SJ , 2022) relating to national values and the role of the Indonesian language as the main pillar of nationalism. Data collection was carried out by sorting reference sources and scientific literature related to national values and the role of the Indonesian language as the main pillar of nationalism. Then it is reviewed and analyzed and presented in a systematic arrangement.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Brief History of Indonesian

Indonesian comes from Malay, which belongs to the Austronesian language family, which has been used as a lingua franca in the archipelago since the early centuries of the modern calendar, at least in its non-formal form (Alek et al., 2010). The term "market malay" is often used to describe this colloquialism. This type is very flexible because it is very effective and easy to understand, has high error tolerance, and can absorb many terms from various languages used by users (Khadim: 2012).

Apart from market Malay, there is also the term High Malay. This term was previously used by royal families in Sumatra, Malaya and Java. This term is more difficult to use because the language is more subtle and full of innuendo than market Malay (Asep: 2020). The Dutch colonial government saw the flexibility of the Malay market as a threat to language and culture (Mulyati: 2007).

The Dutch tried to reduce this by encouraging high Malay language, including the publication of literature in high Malay language by Balai Pustaka. However, many traders passing through Indonesia have already adopted market Malay (Hermawan: 2012).

The Indonesian language is gradually, but surely, developing and evolving. This language has developed very quickly recently so that it has become a modern language that is strong and rich in vocabulary (Sedyawati, et al: 2009).

October 28, 1928, students and teenagers claimed the Youth Pledge. The 1928 Youth Congress Decision Draft included three types of the same determination as follows: "First: We, the sons and daughters of Indonesia, confess that we share one blood, the land of Indonesia. Second: We, sons and daughters of Indonesia, claim to be one nation, Indonesian. Third: We, sons and daughters of Indonesia, uphold the language of unity, Indonesian."

The decision of the youth congress above shows the nationalistic spirit of young people and students at that time to fight for independence and recognition of the Indonesian language throughout the world.

We, today's youth and students, continue to fight for the future, as mentioned above. Students and teenagers must be able to develop a sense of nationalism towards the Indonesian language and be enthusiastic about developing and preserving this language so that it remains alive and is not lost to the eroding of time and technology. We must be able to place Indonesian among other international languages without losing out to foreign languages that have entered and been glorified. To maintain Indonesian as the language of unity, the youth and students of the Republic of Indonesia must unite on October 28 1928.

Indonesian: Source of Nationalism

As stated in the third pledge of the 1928 Youth Pledge, "We sons and daughters of Indonesia uphold the language of unity, Indonesian", Indonesian is considered the national language and is above regional languages.

According to (Arifin et al., 2008:12), the 1945 Constitution included a special article regarding Indonesian as the state language. Therefore, it can be concluded that Indonesian is the state language and national language. Indonesian is very important in this country, but young people and students do not know this (Muhammad : 2012). Indonesian is the essence of the Indonesian nation, and as the next generation, we must maintain and develop it.

In its position, the Indonesian language must be truly understood by all groups, especially young people and students, so that their spirit of patriotism and nationalism continues to be maintained, this is related to the current situation which is becoming more and more of a crisis in the spirit of nationalism. Young people and students are more proud of foreign languages, such as English, Mandarin, Arabic and others, which leave aside our national and state languages, this is because Indonesian is a mother tongue that is easy to understand and does not require special learning (Lan, et al: 2011). In reality, there are still many young people and students who do not know good and correct Indonesian, starting

from basic education level to tertiary level. This is in accordance with the reality that was researched by one of the students the author has supervised. From the results of research on the position and function of the Indonesian language in teaching and learning activities, it can be seen that the majority of students do not use Indonesian properly and correctly, they more often use regional languages with a mixture of foreign languages which clearly destroys the linguistic order that has been standardized in Indonesia. Apart from that, there are still many educators, in this case teachers, in teaching and learning activities who do not use Indonesian effectively, this also affects the mindset of students, so that they are not used to using Indonesian well and correctly, where the final goal will lead to the position and function of the Indonesian language is not well maintained in the eyes of young people and students (Affan, et al: 2016).

The Function of Indonesian as a Source of Strength for Nationalism

Table 1. Arifin's Book (2008:12) States that the Status of Indonesian as a National Language has Several Functions, Such as:

Symbol of National Pride	National Identity Symbol	Inter-citizen, inter-regional, inter-cultural communication tools	Tool to Unify Ethnic Culture and Language
The Indonesian language functions as a symbol of national pride and reflects the socio-cultural values that underlie the feeling of nationality. On the basis of this pride, the Indonesian language must be protected, maintained and developed, and we must also continue to build a sense of pride in its users.	National Identity, which means that the Indonesian language is respected along with the flag and coat of arms of the country. The Indonesian language must have characteristics that are different from the symbols of other countries to fulfill its function. Only when the communities that use it, especially young people and students, develop it without elements of other languages, will Indonesian become unique.	Indonesian has an important role in society and in this country. Because of the Indonesian language, people in society can interact with each other in a way that there are no misunderstandings due to differences in language and socio-cultural backgrounds. By using Indonesian as the only way to communicate, people can travel anywhere in the country.	Language as a means of unifying ethnicity, culture and language means that Indonesian allows harmony between various tribes, cultures and languages in the archipelago without losing tribal identity or loyalty to socio-cultural values and relevant local language backgrounds. A national language also allows society to prioritize national interests over regional or group interests.

Table 2. However, the Status of Indonesian as a State Language has Several Objectives, Including

Official State Language	Instructive Language in Education	Transportation Tools at the National Level	Tools for the Development of Culture, Science and Technology
Indonesian is used as the country's official language in ceremonies, events and other activities. Writing documents, decisions, letters and state speeches is one of these activities.	Except for a few areas that still use their regional languages, such as Aceh, Batak, Sundanese, Java, Madura, Bali and Makasar, Indonesian is very important in the education system throughout Indonesia, from kindergartens to universities.	Indonesian is used in this case to communicate not only between the government and the general public, not only between tribes and between regions, but also between socio-cultural and linguistic communities of the same language.	In this context, Indonesian is the only tool that allows us to build and develop national culture in such a way that Indonesian has characteristics and identity that differentiate it from local culture.

The Relationship Between Indonesian and Nationalism

Indonesian has a very important role and position in the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia, as shown above. Therefore, as young people and students, we must fight to maintain it and develop it.

Language functions in all fields, including education, social, cultural and scientific. Its function as an instructor and liaison in society is very important, enabling our society to develop thoughts and ideas well.

In fact, today's young people and students are starting to lose familiarity with the Indonesian language. This is a fact in society, where people are more proud of being able to speak a foreign language than speaking Indonesian.

The Indonesian language has changed so that the refined order or spelling is no longer appropriate, which causes the order to no longer be appropriate. Foreign languages are considered important for future education, so parents have accustomed their children to using foreign languages at home. As a result, teenagers often no longer use Indonesian. Therefore, it can be concluded that the spirit of Indonesian nationalism towards the Indonesian language is currently in a state of emergency or crisis.

Based on the conclusions above, the author would like to convey several recommendations, including:

First, young people and students must continue to acquire useful skills, especially in the fields of science and technology. Second, by proudly using Indonesian and not glorifying foreign languages, we contribute to the development and maintaining the identity of the Republic of Indonesia. Third, readers must be able to maintain and develop Indonesian language skills.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

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FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic Maintenance of National Values, the Role of Indonesian Language as Nationalism in order to improve this research and add insight to readers.

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